

Spectral Properties of Cubebin

(Mrs.) A. Chatterjee, S. C. Basa and A. B. Ray

Cubebin has been isolated from the fruits of *Piper cubeba* L. and its various spectral properties reported.

Cubebin is a naturally occurring lignan¹ obtained from the unripe fruits of cubeb (*Piper cubeba* L., family, *Piperaceae*) which finds use to stimulate the healing of mucous membranes in chronic diseases. It is one of the first lignans to be examined² and its structure has been conclusively settled³ as I, on the basis of the results of degradative experiments and particularly by its conversion into compounds of known structure.

In the course of our investigations⁴ on the chemical constituents of different *Piper* species, cubebin was isolated from the fruits of *P. cubeba* and we like to keep on record its various spectral properties which have not yet been reported.

Cubebin, $C_{20}H_{20}O_6$, m.p. 133°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -47^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), absorbs in the ultraviolet region; λ_{Max}^{EtOH} 233, 287 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$, 3.79, 3.81 (Carl Zeiss, Model VSU—1) and its absorption characteristics are typical of a methylenedioxy benzene chromophore⁵. The infrared spectrum (Perkin-Elmer, Model—21) of cubebin in the solid phase exhibits strong bands at 925, 1040 and 1245 cm^{-1} for methylenedioxy groupings⁶ and a broad band at 3375 cm^{-1} for a hydroxyl. Other absorption bands of high intensity, discernible in the spectrum, appear at 1505, 1490, 1443 and 810 cm^{-1} . The 60 Mc NMR spectrum (Fig. 1) of cubebin, taken in $CDCl_3$ -DMSO (1:1), exhibits signals corresponding to six aromatic protons around 6.6 δ and four methylenedioxy protons at 5.90 δ . Partly obscured by the methylenedioxy signal is a one proton doublet (5.80 δ , $J=5$ c/s) which disappears on deuterium exchange, obviously represents the lactol hydroxyl of cubebin. The proton flanked between the hydroxyl and the ether oxygen appears virtually as a triplet around 5.10 δ , but changes to a clean doublet ($J=5$ c/s) on deuteration of the hydroxyl proton. A two-proton envelope over a region of 3.32-4.0 δ and a two-proton singlet at 3.22 δ are attributed respectively

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to the two vicinal methine protons and the methylene protons adjacent to the ether oxygen. The four benzylic protons of cubebin merge with the methyl signals of DMSO around 2.53 δ .

FIG. 1

The molecular ion peak at m/e 356, read in the mass spectrum of cubebin is consistent with its molecular composition, $C_{20}H_{20}O_6$. The other important peaks at m/e 338, 203, 136 and 135, discernible in the spectrum correspond to ion fragments, a, b, c and d respectively, the genesis of which is rationalized according to the following modes of fragmentation.

FIG. 2

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. Ultraviolet absorption spectrum was taken in 95% aldehyde-free ethanol, IR spectrum in KBr pellet and NMR spectrum in $CDCl_3$ -DMSO (1:1) in a 60 Mc instrument.

Isolation of cubebin:

Crushed air-dried fruits (250 g.) of *Piper cubeba* were exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in a soxhlet apparatus (36 hr.). The extract was concen-

trated to a thick oil, adsorbed over a bed of neutral alumina in a chromatogram and the column was washed down with benzene-chloroform(1:1) till no oily residue was obtained by evaporation of the eluting solvent. The column was then eluted with chloroform when cubebin migrated out as a white solid which crystallised from methanol in needles (yield 0.5%), m.p. 133°, $[\alpha]_D -47^\circ$ (CHCl₃), M⁺, 356; (Found: C, 67.32; H, 5.67. Calc. for C₂₀H₂₀O₆: C, 67.41; H, 5.61%).

A fresh crop of cubebin (yield—0.8%) was also obtained from the alcoholic extract of the defatted fruits of *P. cubeba* following the method of Haworth & Kelly⁷; semi-carbazone, 143-44° (Lit.⁷ m.p. 144°).

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA-9.

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